

IBN SINA'S SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE

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Abstract. Was Ibn Sina just a great physician and famous philosopher? Ibn Sina had a different world from the beginning. The encyclopedic scholar deeply studied the religious and secular sciences of his time and created works related to Sufism with a deep and comprehensive understanding of the true meaning of the Islamic religion. We witness the clear illumination of human body, soul, and soul relationships.

Keywords: philosophy, manuscripts, library, Medicine, achievement, treatment, Doctor, science

Introduction. In Suleymaniye Library of Turkey there are Ibn Sina's 263 works are stored, and they are related to the following subjects:

1	Related to philosophy	89
2	related to logics	11
3	Related to philosophy of religion	53
4	Related to tasawwuf (sufism)	5
5	Related to linguistics	2
6	Related to literature	12
7	Related to maths	7
8	Related to physics	2
9	Related to chemistry	2
10	Related to medicine	58
11	Related to politics	1
12	Related to geography	1
13	Related to astronomy	7

Methodology. All these works are believed to be manuscripts copied between 1022 and 1728. There are also small works of Ibn Sina, in which the scholar expressed his views on epistemology, ontology, theology and metaphysics. The correspondence of the encyclopedist with Abu Rayhan Beruni is also located in the library complex.

There are 58 copies of scholar's work "The Canons of Medicine" kept in Sulaymaniyah. A Latin translation of the Laws of Medicine dates from 1510 and depicts Avicenna on the cover, crowned between Galen and Hippocrates.

The encyclopedic scholar was able to demonstrate his perfection in every field of science. Here are the names of some works of the thinker:

<p>Philosophical works: "Donishnoma", "Kitab un-najot", "Kitab ush-shifo" and others.</p> <p>Philosophical stories: "Hayy ibn Yakzon", "Solomon and Ibsol", "Tayr story" and others.</p>
<p>Regarding logic: "al-Mantiq", "Ishorot va Tanbihat", "Najot" and others.</p>
<p>Regarding the philosophy of religion: "Treatise on Miraj", "Risola fi anna lo mahofa lilmavt" ("Treatise on the absence of danger of death"), "Al-Hasil wa al-mahsul", "Risala lo saodata wa lo shakavata fi haza-l-olam ala -l-itlaq" ("The treatise that there is no absolute happiness and unhappiness in this world").</p>
<p>Related to Tasawwuf (Sufism): "Fi ahwal an-nafs" ("About the state of the soul), "Risalat fi tazkiyat an-nafs" ("A treatise on keeping the soul pure), "Goodness and evil".</p>
<p>Related the language: "Lison al-arab" ("Arabic language") and others.</p>
<p>About literature: "Risolatut-tayr" (Bird's message), "Solomon and Ibsol"</p>
<p>Regarding mathematics: "Danishnoma", "Ash-shifo"</p>
<p>Regarding physics: "Danishnoma", "Ash-shifa"</p> <p>In the field of mechanics: "Aqllar meyori" ("Miyorul-uqul") written in Dari (Perso-Tajik) language consists of five chapters.</p>

On chemistry: he wrote two works.
About medicine: More than fifty-eight works
Regarding astronomy: “Al-Hudud al-Ajram al-Samoviya”(“Boundaries of Heavenly Bodies”, Astronomy section of “Donishnama”(this section consists of 9 chapters)

The fate of Ibn Sina's books was not as good as expected all the time. In particular, in 1661, the work “Kitab ash shifa” was burned in a fire by order of the Caliph of Baghdad.

Ibn Sina is not only a famous scientist and physician, but also a talented poet and writer. He wrote his poems in the form of ruboi. In his poems, he calls on humanity to be truthful and conscientious, to learn the basics of Science in order to reveal the secrets of nature, to patiently study deep and Exact Sciences, to raise the name of man to even higher heights.

Ibn Sina's greatest achievement was the deep mastery of all the sciences of his time, his life, as well as the ability to write deeply meaningful works in the field of these sciences and sculpt himself in the world scientific world.

Ibn Sina, whose life was devoted to science, did not start a family. Throughout his life, he was engaged in scientific work and treatment of patients, teaching science to young students.

Juzjani noted that Ibn Sina was a very energetic person in the physical aspect. However, wanderings in the city-by-city wanderings, continuous work at night, some kind of persecution, layoffs negatively affected the health of the alloma. The alloma suffered from collapse (colitis) disease. When the disease worsened, it also became epilepsy. As a result of this pain, Abu Ali Hussein Ibn-Sina died in Ramadan of 428 Ah, that is, on June 24, 1037. His grave is in Hamadon.

Scholar’s hard work, **love of science, accompanying practice with theory, serious attention to each patient, being able to illuminate the essence of the medicine** from simple to complex in logical consistency, will leave everyone who

knows how to apply the necessary, accurate phrases lol. He has written about 450 works, his entire life is impenetrable to humanity, the perfection of his works on teaching him Health, thinking, correct and rational thinking, and the fact that the Almighty is a genius person.

Indeed, the thinker himself wrote that “for me the meaning of my life is more important than the amount of days of my life lived.”

The continuation of accurate and accurate information about the life and scientific activities of Ibn Sina was continued by Abu Ubayd Al-Juzjani. This resource is considered the most unique for us.

Ibn Sina and his scientific, spiritual, medical heritage, a number of caromats, a valiant man, a priest philosopher Abu Saeed Maykhani, were amazed at the simple perception of hard work, diligence, searchability, mobility, talent, thinking, unseen in him: “he took the science that Allah gave me through his labor.” Historians such as Al Qasriy, Narshakhi, Suyuti, Sayid Yahya were also bokhabar from the science of Ibn Sina ghayb and simiyah, to which plants would tell their healing properties “left inscriptions on the grave.

When we say that Ibn Sina really devoted his whole life to human health and its preservation activities, we would never have made a mistake.

Having tried all aspects of mental and logical cognition in medicine, the philosopher's alloma revealed the secrets of health, supporting in practice all methods of scientific cognition.

According to Ibn Sina's point of view, quality is not lost in quantity. Likewise, the uniqueness and integrity of quality and quantity, the need for each other, do not mean at all that they have joined each other.

In philosophy, **quality** is an internal certainness of a thing, the uniqueness of its series of features, signs, properties. Quality-means the self-equality of the thing, the process. The adjective expresses the constancy, relative stability of the subject: “clean” blood, “dirty blood”, “clean body”, “dirty body” , “girl”, “girl”, “woman”, “mother”, “grandmother”, etc.

The **adjective** is referred to in Arabic as “mood”. In medicine, the adjective will be expressed as follows: health, disease, strength, irritability (weakness), colorism, (color fading), States of change in body color, smell, sound, heat, cold, humidity, dryness, condition, knowledge, Tam, sound-sound, etc. Qualitatively, pain is divided into fifteen types:

1. Translated as” scratching pain " or ("stinging pain");
2. throbbing pain;
3. prick pain;
4. pressing pain;
5. stretching pain;
6. tearing pain;
7. throbbing pain; (“fracture pain")
8. sluggish pain;
9. fingering pain;
10. simillab pain;
11. fighting pain;
12. whining pain;
13. pain when feeling heaviness;
14. throbbing pain;
15. aching burning pain;

The alloma also divided diseases into adjectives into several types: Тузаладиган касалликлар;

1. Non-healing diseases;
2. ” Old " – chronic diseases;
3. Acute fractions;
4. Common disease;
5. Complex disease, etc.

The thing is that the processes differ from each other in quantitative aspects, in addition to qualitative certainty. Quantity is characterized by the size, measure,

weight, speed of movement, intensity, viscosity or, conversely, continuity, duration of the subject.

The quantity is called “kamiyya” in Arabic. Example: number, size, thickness, length, brevity, linearity, fineness, continuity, volume, point, dimension, etc.

Ibn Sina's achievement was that he was able to distinguish between signs of quality and quantity. For this reason, too, distinguished”quantity diseases “from”quality diseases. Quantity diseases are divided by The Thinker:

1. Quantity growth diseases;
2. Quantity reduction diseases.

“Quantitative diseases” are distinguished by **an increase** or decrease in size, decrease. The alloma, as an example, gives an example of enlargement - “elephant leg disease”, hypertrophies. “**Elephant disease– elephantiasis-elfantiasis**. In this case, the paw becomes larger and larger, as in the case of venereal expansion disease. Like the extreme size of the penis – it is called **priapism's** disease, or they resemble a disease that occurs in a person called Nicomakh; all its organs have become so large that they are incapable of moving.

Diminution-the inability of organs to grow, atrophies are examples, such as a tongue twister, a diminution of the eyeball or the wilting of the (whole torso).

Number (PCs) diseases are divided into two:

1. Natural number (PCs) diseases;
2. Abnormal number (PCs) diseases

Diseases of the thigh (PCs)it is natural that they become the opposite sex, as excess finger and unevenly grown teeth;

In cases of abnormal number (PCs) diseases, an excess that has grown on the limb (sil'a) or like a stone. An example of diseases of the formation of stones is the disease of quantity PCs. Thigh disease or deficiency will come from gender: it will be congenital, like a person born without a finger, either this deficiency will not be natural, like a cut of a finger.

He paid attention to the presence of “diseases that occur due to violation of continuity. In his work “Wisdom“, “two types of quantity: the first is” absolute “when”continuity" is expressed in Arabic. The second is faceted, expressed in Arabic as “munfasil”. Everything in being, the subject and in the process, quantity and quality are inseparable, manifested in uniqueness. In the presence of nature, there is no immutable object itself. But all the nature being changes within its framework.

This topic is logically continued in the lecture “the concept of Ibn Sina on the norm and mizoj”.

Ishq is one of the issues of philosophy. Body, mind, spirit, work - these are categories of dialectical connection. Ibn Sina's "treatise of Ishq" consists of the following seven chapters:

1. About the power of Love, which everyone has in their nature;
2. About work in lifeless soups;
3. About the existence of Ishq even in creatures and animals with the power they receive from food;
4. About the presence of alkali in living-powered creatures with animalistic ores;
5. About love in those who have beauty, youth femininity;
6. About the work of hearts close to Allah;
7. Wives of seasons.

In the work of Abu Ali Ibn Sina, “Ishq” is extremely multifaceted, complex and deep in essence. Ibn Sina divided love into:

1. Physical labor
2. Psychic Love has separated.

Results. The scholar alloma divides alkali into five different in essence. But for Ibn Sina herself, two types of love are most important – the work of young people and the beautiful, and the divine work. Analyzing love through the “mirror” of form and content, emotion and reason, the scholar believes that a person who loves a beautiful image only for his beauty, loves it only because of an animal feeling. But

a person who loves beauty spiritually gains his positive qualities. Therefore, when a person is a sage, he observes beauty, then his qualities increase. In Ibn Sina's world of Ishq, lovers are always able to control their sexual feelings, while thanks to Ishq they are able to absorb more noble qualities in themselves, striving to bring their souls to the achievement of the qualities of the status of the highest spirit. The purity of spiritual love is at a high point. Hence, moral purity is also at the top in love.

CONCLUSION

1. In his works on medicine as a great doctor of the Middle Ages, he saw the preservation of human health as the meaning of his life.

2. Ibn Sina showed in his philosophical works the factors of improving the human psyche, bringing a person to perfection through science, scattering seeds of goodness in his soul. The materialistic direction of the scientist's philosophy was based on experience in the field of Medicine.

3. He came up with the idea that being is eternal, it develops according to the laws of nature.

4. If Beruni was a measureer of the norm of Planet Earth, Ibn Sina was a measureer of the norms of human health and patient condition, and Ulugbek was a measureer of stars.

5. Ibn Sina, as a doctor and philosopher, showed that the human body, the soul-is interconnected with different members of the tongue, is formed in harmony with each other. For the first time, Alkali was divided into physical (anatomical) and spiritual (spiritual) types. No one had studied love-love until Ibn Sina without a double anatomical and spiritual.

6. Enriched the concept of "divine work" in content. A person is obliged to find strength, will in himself so that he can overcome the cardinal, mischievous, zamima features in his alloma. Only then will the first step towards the "divine love" be able to overcome.

7. Intelligence in love should also be a priority. For avisenna, the conscious spirit in moral love makes a free movement. A man who loves a beautiful

image only for his beauty, Abu Ali Ibn Sina believes, loves only because of the animalistic feeling. But a person who loves beauty spiritually gains his positive qualities. ... "love pure love, which increases the Supreme generosity and virtue, it brings a person only to good. Ishq zeyri, which interferes with rational consciousness, is a Moral Animal affair... There is no sin in love, which is realized by the eye and the feeling, which only generates contentment with hugs and kisses. Because it only leads to good... So, does the morals of the scrub bring the lover to maturity or reduce it to the level of an animal? . This is the basis of his doctrine of Ishq.

Ibn Sina's words that were in tune with his thoughts of animalistic, Satanic emotion were also expressed by his great contemporary Abu Raykhan Beruni in his work "India" through the following phrases: "it is impossible for a people to live without marriage, because marriage prevents the growth of lust, which is naughty, disgusting to the mind. Anyone who has observed the life of animals living in pairs will realize that marriage is a necessity when they see that every male animal is satisfied with its female and other animals leave them as they are. Irregular sex in humans is a scoundrel, which is even more radical than animal".

Ibn Sina rightly states that " the unconscious animal is by nature a characteristic feature... in order to create something similar to himself, writes" love is engaged, plants are the same." The alloma believes that " what appears will certainly disappear one day, so their species must be preserved. Therefore, each species of animal and nabobot, according to the order rationally established by Allah, tries to continue its genus, species. When we express in modern ecological expressions this idea first: in the presence of nature, it means that each species has its own norm, that is, its average number of species, and secondly, that it is natural for birth and death to leave their offspring in maintaining the norm – the average amount of this species. Thirdly, it also emphasizes the importance of maintaining biological species diversity.

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